

A Natural Remedy for Respiratory Relief

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Abstract:

Herbal cough syrup is a natural, effective, and safe remedy for respiratory issues such as coughs, congestion, and sore throats. This syrup combines the therapeutic properties of various herbs, including tulsi, ginger, turmeric, and mint, to provide rapid relief from cough symptoms. The formulation is designed to soothe and calm the throat, reduce inflammation, and boost immunity. With its unique blend of bioactive compounds, this syrup offers a holistic approach to respiratory health. Syrup that have been developed using herbal medication Dosage are also included. Most of the Herbal Syrup Was Originally derived from plant herbal Medicine Refers to use extract to plant for medicinal Purpose.

Tulsi Leaf extract is added as an anti bacterial agent to Stop the growth of bacteria and jaggery and Alcohol are used as Today Syrup is used to treat variety of the illness and relieve disease symptoms. Herbal syrup provide a Holistic Alternative to synthetic cough suppressant with a focus on soothing the Thorat, Reducing inflammation And easing cough symptoms caused by condition such as the common cold bronchitis or allergies.

Keywords: herbal cough syrup, natural remedy, respiratory relief, tulsi, ginger, turmeric, mint.

Introduction

Herbal cough syrup is a natural, plant-based remedy designed to provide relief from coughs, congestion, and respiratory discomfort. With the increasing demand for alternative and complementary therapies, herbal cough syrups have gained popularity worldwide. These syrups harness the therapeutic properties of various herbs, spices, and botanicals to soothe and calm the throat, reduce inflammation, and boost

It is defined as a prepared and combination on and concentration decoction with jaggery either some time use alcohol.

Cough - Cough is a natural reflex action that occurs when the body needs to clear the airways (thorax and lungs) of irritant mucus or foreign particles. Herbal cough syrup or similar herbal remedies for cough and respiratory ailments have been used for thousands of years with roots in traditional medicine around the world. The use of medicinal plants to treat cough and other respiratory issues can be traced back to ancient civilization where natural remedies were cornerstones of healthcare.

1) modern era: since in 19th century health herbal remedies have been integrated into more formalized medicinal practice in Europe and North America

2) Ayurveda (India) dating back over 5000 years ayurveda the traditional Indian systems of medicines has used herbs like tulsi, pudina, ginger turmeric to treat cough and respiratory Cough medication is not only suppress the cough but also the relieve cough caused by coughing repeatedly extrathoracic symptoms such as back pain, headache, fever, malaise for want symptomatic treatment. Treatment for a productive cough may include correcting the abnormalities that causes sputum production or changing the composition of the secretion to make excretions simpler syrup are present in high amount of predispose then to the bacteria infection so they often use as a preservative

Types of cough

1. dry cough: Dry cough doesn't produce mucus because their mucus blocking the lungs or airway nothing comes out when you cough this lack of mucus (phlegm) makes it an unproductive cough.

2. wet cough: wet a productive or cough is that brings up fluids such as phlegm it can indicate a respiratory infection (COPD) and other conditions

Some herbal Ingredients present in cough syrups

1.Tulsi

Introduction to Tulsi

Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*), also known as Holy Basil, is a sacred plant in Hinduism and a revered herb in Ayurvedic medicine. Native to the Indian subcontinent, Tulsi has been cultivated for over 3,000 years for its medicinal, spiritual, and cultural significance.

Biological Constituents

Family:	Lamiaceae
Genus:	Ocimum
Species	O. sanctum
Common Names:	Holy Basil, Tulsi, Sacred Basil

Mechanism of Action:

1. **Anti-inflammatory:** Tulsi contains eugenol, ursolic acid, and rosmarinic acid, which help reduce inflammation in the respiratory tract, soothing irritated tissues and reducing the cough reflex.
2. **Immunomodulatory:** Tulsi enhances the immune response, helping the body fight off infections that cause cough.
3. **Antimicrobial:** It has broad-spectrum antimicrobial properties against bacteria and viruses, helping treat cough caused by respiratory infections.
4. **Antitussive:** Tulsi acts on the central nervous system to suppress the cough reflex.

Pathophysiology:

In conditions like bronchitis or asthma, where inflammation and irritation of the respiratory tract cause persistent coughing, Tulsi reduces the inflammatory response and soothes the mucosa, which decreases the cough reflex. In cases of infectious cough, Tulsi's antimicrobial properties help clear infections, reducing the stimulus that triggers the cough.

Chemical Constituents:

Volatile oils -	Ex. Eugenol
Flavonoids -	Ex.orientin
Phenolic acid-	Ex.Rosmarinic acid
Terpenoids -	Ex.ursolic acid

Pharmacological Properties:

1. **Antimicrobial:** inhibits growth of bacteria, viruses, and fungi
2. **Anti-inflammatory:** reduces inflammation and oxidative stress
3. **Antioxidant:** protects against cell damage and aging
4. **Immunomodulatory:** enhances immune system function
5. **Adaptogenic:** helps body adapt to stress

Pudina

Introduction to Pudina

Pudina (*Mentha piperita*), commonly known as Peppermint or Mint, is a popular herb in Ayurvedic medicine and culinary traditions. Native to Europe and the Middle East, Pudina has been cultivated for over 2,000 years for its refreshing, cooling, and medicinal properties.

Botanical Information:

Family:	Lamiaceae
Genus :	Mentha
Species :	M.piperita
Common name:	Peppermint, Pudina, Mint

Mechanism of Action:

1. **Menthol:** The active compound in peppermint, menthol, acts as a mild anesthetic and decongestant, soothing the throat and reducing cough triggers.

2. **Bronchodilator:** Menthol helps open the airways by relaxing bronchial muscles, making it easier to breathe.

3. Antimicrobial: Peppermint has antimicrobial properties that help fight infections causing cough.

Pathophysiology:

In dry coughs, menthol reduces irritation by desensitizing the cough receptors in the throat and airways, which helps suppress the cough reflex. In productive coughs linked to colds or respiratory infections, peppermint clears nasal and bronchial congestion, allowing better airflow and reducing the need to cough.

Chemical Constituents:

Volatile oils	Ex. Menthol
Flavonoids	Ex. Luteolin
Phenolic acid	Ex. Rosmarinic acid
Terpenoids	Ex. limonene

Pharmacological Properties:

1. Cooling and refreshing effects
2. Antimicrobial: inhibits growth of bacteria, viruses, and fungi
3. Anti-inflammatory: reduces inflammation and oxidative stress
4. Antispasmodic: relaxes muscles and reduces cramps
5. Digestive aid: relieves indigestion, nausea, and irritable bowel syndrome (IBS)

Turmeric

Introduction of turmeric

Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) is a bright yellow-orange spice derived from the rhizome (underground stem) of a plant in the ginger family. It has been used for thousands of years, both as a culinary spice and in traditional medicine, particularly in India and Southeast Asia.

Botanical Information:

Family:	Zingiberaceae
Genus:	Curcuma
Species :	C.longa
Common Names :	Turmeric, Haldi

Mechanism of Action:

- 1. Anti-inflammatory:** Curcumin reduces inflammation in the respiratory tract, soothing irritated airways and reducing the cough reflex, particularly in conditions like bronchitis or asthma.
- 2. Antioxidant:** Turmeric's antioxidants protect lung tissue from oxidative stress caused by infections or irritants, promoting healing and reducing the frequency of coughing.
- 3. Antimicrobial:** Curcumin has antibacterial, antiviral, and antifungal effects, helping fight infections that lead to cough, such as the common cold or respiratory infections.
- 4. Mucolytic:** Turmeric can help break down mucus, making it easier to expel in productive (wet) coughs.

Pathophysiology:

Cough reflex is triggered by irritation or infection in the airways. Turmeric reduces inflammation and clears mucus, calming the cough reflex by addressing the underlying irritation or infection. In wet coughs, it helps loosen mucus, while in dry coughs, it soothes the irritated respiratory linings. Overall, turmeric's anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial effects help reduce the inflammation and infection that often trigger coughing, making it useful for both dry and productive coughs.

Chemical Constituents:

Curcuminoids	Ex. curcumin
Volatile oil	Ex. Turmerone
Flavonoids	Ex. quercetin
Polysaccharides	Ex. starch

Pharmacological Properties:

1. Anti-inflammatory: reduces inflammation and oxidative stress
2. Antimicrobial: inhibits growth of bacteria, viruses, and fungi
3. Antioxidant: protects against cell damage and aging
4. Immunomodulatory: enhances immune system function
5. Anti-cancer: inhibits cancer cell growth and metastasis

Ginger

Introduction to Ginger

Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) is a versatile, ancient spice and herb native to Asia. For over 3,000 years, Ginger has been cultivated for its medicinal, culinary, and spiritual significance.

Botanical Information:

Family:	Zingiberaceae
Genus	Zingiber
Species	Z.officinale
Common Names	Ginger, adrek,Zingiber

Mechanism of Action:

- 1.Anti-inflammatory:** Ginger contains compounds like gingerol and shogaol, which reduce inflammation in the respiratory tract.
- 2.Antitussive:** Ginger can inhibit the cough reflex by acting on sensory receptors in the respiratory tract.
- 3.Bronchodilator:** It helps relax the bronchial smooth muscles, which can reduce the severity of cough in conditions like asthma.

Pathophysiology:

In cases of asthma or chronic cough, ginger reduces bronchoconstriction, easing breathing and decreasing the need to cough. By reducing inflammation and irritation, ginger suppresses the reflex triggers in the upper airways, thus calming dry coughs. In wet coughs, ginger's expectorant properties help mobilize and clear mucus, making the cough more productive.

Chemical Constituents:

Gingerols	Ex.gingerol
Volatile oil	Ex.zinngiberene,bisabolol
Flavonoids	Ex .querce
Phenolic acids	Ex.ferulic acid

Pharmacological Properties:

1. Anti-inflammatory: reduces inflammation and oxidative stress
2. Antimicrobial: Inhibits growth of bacteria, viruses, and fungi
3. Antioxidant: protects against cell damage and aging
4. Anti-emetic: relieves nausea and vomiting
5. Digestive aid: relieves indigestion, bloating, and gas

Fennel

Introduction of Fennel

Fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare*) is a highly aromatic and flavorful herb native to the Mediterranean region, widely used in both culinary and medicinal applications. It belongs to the carrot family (Apiaceae) and is known for its feathery leaves, yellow flowers, and distinctive flavor that resembles anise or licorice.

Botanical Information:

Family	Apiaceae
Genus	Foeniculum
Species	F.vulgare
Common Names	Fennel ,saunf

Mechanism of Action:

1. **Expectorant:** Fennel helps loosen and expel mucus, making it effective for productive (wet) coughs by thinning mucus in the respiratory tract.
2. **Antispasmodic:** Fennel relaxes the bronchial muscles, reducing spasms that cause coughing fits, especially helpful in dry coughs.

3. **Anti-inflammatory:** Fennel reduces inflammation in the respiratory system, soothing irritated airways and reducing the cough reflex.

4. **Antimicrobial:** Its essential oils (like anethole) have antibacterial and antiviral properties, helping fight respiratory infections that cause cough.

5. **Antioxidant:** Fennel's antioxidants help protect the respiratory tract from further irritation and damage, promoting healing.

Pathophysiology:

Cough reflex is triggered by irritation or infection in the airways. Fennel reduces airway inflammation and relaxes bronchial muscles, helping clear mucus and soothe irritated tissues.

In wet coughs, fennel acts as an expectorant, promoting the clearance of mucus, while in dry coughs, its antispasmodic action suppresses coughing by calming the airways. Overall, Fennel's anti-inflammatory, expectorant, and antispasmodic properties make it effective for treating both productive and dry coughs.

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Chemical Constituents:

Volatile oil	Ex.anethoel
Flavonoids	Ex. Querctin
Phenolic acid	Ex.ferulic acid
Terpenoids	Ex, limonene

Pharmacological Properties:

1. Carminative: relieves gas and bloating
2. Antispasmodic: relaxes muscles and reduces cramps
3. Anti-inflammatory: reduces inflammation and oxidative stress
4. Antimicrobial: inhibits growth of bacteria, viruses, and fungi
5. Digestive aid: relieves indigestion, nausea, and irritable bowel syndrome (IBS)

Ajwain

Introduction to Ajwain

Ajwain is an annual herb native to India and the Middle East. Also known as Ajwan, Omam, or Bishop's Weed, Ajwain has been used for centuries in traditional medicine, cooking, and spiritual practices.

Botanical Information:

Family	Apiaceae
Genus	Trachyspermum

Species	T.ammi
Common Names	Ajwain, omam

Mechanism of Action:

- 1. Bronchodilation:** Thymol relaxes the bronchial muscles, opening the airways and easing breathing, which reduces coughing caused by airway constriction (e.g., asthma).
- 2. Expectorant:** Ajwain helps loosen and thin mucus, making it easier to expel during a productive (wet) cough.
- 3. Antitussive:** It suppresses the cough reflex by reducing irritation in the throat and airways, helpful for dry, non-productive coughs.
- 4. Anti-inflammatory:** Ajwain reduces inflammation in the respiratory tract, decreasing sensitivity and irritation that trigger

Pathophysiology:

Cough reflex is triggered by irritation or inflammation in the respiratory tract. Ajwain targets inflammation, infection, and mucus buildup, calming the cough reflex by reducing the stimuli that cause it. In wet coughs, Ajwain promotes mucus clearance, while in dry coughs, it soothes and suppresses the cough reflex, reducing airway irritation. Overall, Ajwain's bronchodilator, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial effects address both the causes and symptoms of different types of cough.

Chemical Constituents:

Volatile oil	Ex.thymol
Flavonoids	Ex.quercetin
Phenolic acids	Ex.ferulic acid

Terpenoids	Ex- limonene
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Pharmacological Properties:

1. Carminative: relieves gas and bloating
2. Antispasmodic: relaxes muscles and reduces cramps
3. Anti-inflammatory: reduces inflammation and oxidative stress
4. Antimicrobial: inhibits growth of bacteria, viruses, and fungi
5. Digestive aid: relieves indigestion, nausea, and irritable bowel syndrome (IBS)

Jaggery

Nutritional Value

Energy :	383kcl
Carbohydrates :	97g
Fiber :	0.5g
Protein :	05g
Fat:	0.5g

Minerals :	Iron, Potassium, Calcium, Magnesium
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Mechanism of Action:

- 1. Mucolytic Effect:** Jaggery helps in loosening mucus, making it easier to expel, which is particularly useful in productive (wet) coughs.
- 2. Soothing and Demulcent:** It coats the throat, reducing irritation and soothing inflamed tissues, thereby helping with dry cough.
- 3. Antioxidant:** Jaggery contains minerals and antioxidants that help boost the immune system, supporting faster recovery from infections that cause cough.
- 4. Warming Effect:** Jaggery has a warming effect, which helps dilate blood vessels and improve circulation, aiding in clearing the respiratory passages.

Pathophysiology:

Cough reflex is triggered by irritation in the respiratory tract due to mucus or inflammation. Jaggery helps reduce throat irritation and clears mucus, addressing both dry and wet coughs by calming the cough reflex and supporting mucus expulsion.

Health Benefits:

- 1. Rich in minerals and antioxidants**
- 2. Natural sweetener, lower glycemic index than refined sugar**
- 3. Aids digestion and relieves constipation**
- 4. Boosts immunity and energy levels**
- 5. Supports bone health**

Advantages and disadvantages of Herbal cough syrups

Conclusion:

Herbal cough syrup is a natural, effective, and safe remedy for respiratory issues. The synergy of herbs like Tulsi, Pudina, Turmeric, Ginger, Fennel, and Ajwain provides rapid relief from cough symptoms, soothes the throat, and supports immune function.

References:

1. The information has been collected from article by Chung KF, Mazzone SB. Cough. In: Broaddus VC, King TE, Ernst JD, et al, eds. Murray and Nadel's Textbook of Respiratory Medicine.

7th ed. Philadelphia, PA: Elsevier; 2022.

2. This above information was collected from an article by Shahnaz sultana , Andleeb Khan et al , 2016 published by Research gate.

3. The above information was collected from an article by Dr.AsfiyaNajmi published by Healty bazar 2023.

4. SeemaGairola. Vikas Gupta (2010) et al. A Review on Herbal Antitussives And Expectorants. Department of Biochemistry, PGIMER, Chandigarh, Volume 5, Issue 2. November-December 2010: Article-002.

5. Akula Nikhil Prashant. Dr. K. V. Subramanyam (2015) et al. Development and Evaluation of HerbalCough Syrup. International Reviewed Journal For Pharmaceutical and Medical Research and Technology 2278-4357, ICV-84.87

6. Jafarzadeh M. Pourkhalili K. Bahmani M, Ahmadi B. Baharyand-Ahmadi BB Ratician-Kopaei M. Medicinal plants and secondary metabolites for cough Treatment: A systematic review. Iranian Journal of Public Health. 2015 Jun 1:44(6):685.

7. Rajacl A. Barikbin B. Moghadamnia AA. Mohammadi M. Arjomand Y. Mohammadi-Kamalabadi M, Khaksari M. Effect of a herbal syrup on cough in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: A randomized controlled trial. Iranian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research. 2015;14(2):557.

8. Shahnaz sultana , Andleeb Khan et al , 2016 Various herbs used in herbal cough syrup published by Research gate.

9. Dr.Javesh K. PatilDipali R. Mali, et al (2019), Formulation And Evaluation of Herbal Syrup. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research. VOL 8 Issue 6, 1061- 1067